

Modeling and experimental analysis of hybrid cantilever structures with embedded MFC patch

Abstract This study presents the modeling and analysis of a composite structure incorporating an embedded Macro Fiber Composite (MFC) patch. MFC actuators are available in several variants, with types P1 and P2 being the most commonly used. ~~In this paper Aa~~ an electromechanical model of the hybrid structure is developed, and experimental procedures are outlined for identifying selected system parameters. In the first phase of the study, two separate cantilever beam specimens ~~were-are~~ investigated - one with an embedded P1 patch and the other with a P2 patch. Their behaviors ~~were-analyzed-are tested~~ and compared to identify and critically assess the advantages and limitations associated with each MFC type. In the second phase, a more complex system - a bistable cantilever shell - ~~was~~ examined. The choice of the appropriate MFC type (P1 or P2) for this structure ~~was~~ based on the findings obtained in the first phase. For the system incorporating the selected MFC patch, the dynamic response ~~was~~ analyzed in the vicinity of both stable equilibrium states, which are characterized by significantly different levels of pre-strain and pre-stress. The study concludes with ~~a summary of the findings from both phases of the investigation, highlighting their implications~~ for the design of smart composite structures with integrated MFC patches.

Keywords: ~~lumped~~ electromechanical model, Macro Fiber Composite transducer, electromechanical coupling estimation, experimental research

1. Introduction

A hybrid structure can be defined as a combination of different materials or components connected to achieve optimal or adaptive properties. In the literature, particular attention has been given to multilayer hybrid structures. Typically, the core of such a system is a layered composite, within which conventional or smart materials are incorporated either between or outside the layers. In classical applications, fiber-reinforced composites with full or partial metallic layers are often employed. Such modifications aim to enhance specific structural characteristics. For example, in [1], glass-epoxy and carbon-epoxy composites with additional titanium layers were investigated. The incorporation of metallic layers was intended to control structural deformation during low-velocity impacts. The study demonstrated that this modification significantly influenced damage propagation. Another example of a conventional modification is the inclusion of metal strips within bistable structures [2]. Aluminum strips embedded in a carbon-epoxy shell altered the curvature of the structure and affected the force required for snap-through behavior. More advanced modification capabilities can be achieved using smart layers. Additional materials with controllable properties include magnetorheological fluids, piezoelectric elements, and shape memory alloy (SMA) fibers. Magnetorheological fluids can vary their apparent viscosity in response to a magnetic field, which can be utilized to increase damping in hybrid structures. In [3], a three-layer beam was studied in which the middle layer was filled with a magnetorheological fluid. A comparison of the beam's vibrations with and without an applied magnetic field showed that activating the fluid effectively reduced structural vibrations. However, this approach provides only passive or semi-active control by dissipating energy. Greater functionality is offered by shape memory alloy fibers, which can change stiffness and shape in response to temperature. Research on laminated composite plates embedded with SMA wires is presented in [4], where the authors analyzed the influence of temperature on natural frequencies and the thermal buckling behavior of the hybrid structure. Piezoelectric materials appear to offer the

most versatile application potential, as they enable both vibration control and energy harvesting. An example of how fiber orientation affects the dynamic behavior of such a structure is found in [5]. However, embedding individual piezoelectric fibers poses significant manufacturing challenges. A more practical solution involves using prefabricated piezoelectric patches. One of the leading manufacturers of such elements is Smart Material Corp. [6], which produces Macro Fiber Composite (MFC) patches. MFC patches feature a complex internal structure, where the electrode configuration, in addition to the piezoelectric fibers themselves, plays a crucial role. A key advantage is their high flexibility, which allows integration without significantly altering the host structure's stiffness. Depending on the electrode configuration, MFCs can generate an electric field either along or across the patch. This distinction gives rise to two main types: P1, which utilizes the d33 piezoelectric effect, and P2, which utilizes the d31 effect. These types differ not only in the direction of the induced electric field but also in capacitance and voltage characteristics. According to the manufacturer, P1-type elements are intended primarily for vibration control, while P2-type elements are designed for energy harvesting. An application of MFC-P1 patches for vibration control is presented in [7], where MFCs were installed on composite rotor blades. Applying voltage to the patches resulted in measurable changes in the rotor's natural frequencies. A contrasting application is described in [8], where an MFC-P2 patch was attached to a cantilever beam. As the beam deformed during vibration, the patch generated voltage via the direct piezoelectric effect. However, the findings in [9] depart from these general guidelines. In this experimental study, a bistable shell was tested, where the snap-through phenomenon led to significant changes in the equilibrium position, accompanied by large strains in the MFC patch. The authors observed that P1 elements performed more reliably under these demanding conditions, while P2 elements were more prone to damage. These findings highlighted the need for a direct comparison of the performance of P1 and P2 types under similar conditions - an area insufficiently explored in the current literature.

In the present work, two types of cantilever composite structures with embedded MFC patches were investigated. The first configuration involved two identical cantilever composite beams - one with an MFC-P1 patch and the other with an MFC-P2 patch. Experimental studies examining both the direct and inverse piezoelectric effects enabled a comparative evaluation of the effectiveness of each element, highlighting their respective advantages and limitations. The second configuration consisted of a bistable cantilever composite shell equipped with an MFC-P1 patch. In this case, experiments revealed differences in MFC performance during vibrations around the two stable equilibrium states, corresponding to different initial stress/strain states in the patch. In addition, a lumped-parameter model of the hybrid structure was developed, incorporating both mechanical and electrical domains. This model was used to analyze the system's basic characteristics and to illustrate the parameter identification procedures. The combined experimental and modeling approach provides insights into the capabilities of MFC-based hybrid structures for both vibration control and energy harvesting applications.

2. Electromechanical model of hybrid structure

By adding a piezoelectric layer to the structure, an electromechanical system is obtained. A lumped ~~mass-parameter~~ model of such a system is presented in Fig. 1. In this schematic, two subsystems - mechanical and electrical - along with the coupling mechanism between them, can be distinguished. The diagram serves as a mechanical analogy of the electromechanical structure. The first, ~~mechanical,~~ subsystem represents a simplified model of a cantilever structure. The parameters included are:

k , c , and m - representing the equivalent stiffness, damping, and mass, respectively,
 P - the external excitation force,

w - the transverse displacement at a selected point of the structure, such as its free end.

The second subsystem describes the electrical domain, reflecting both the inherent properties of the piezoelectric patch and any additional components (e.g., amplifier or energy harvester). The generalized coordinate q denotes the electric charge, or equivalently, the current in the circuit. The primary electrical parameters include:

L - ~~the~~ inductance,

C - ~~the~~ capacitance of the piezoelectric element,

R - ~~the~~ load resistance (representing the harvesting element),

U - ~~the~~ applied external voltage (representing an amplifier or controller output).

The two subsystems are coupled. In the mechanical analogy, this coupling is represented by a lever mechanism [10]. The lever has two arms of lengths 1 and α , where α is the electromechanical coupling coefficient. The coupling is considered to operate within the linear range. The resulting lumped model can be described by a set of coupled differential equations [11]:

$$\begin{aligned} m\ddot{w} + kw + c\dot{w} + \alpha \frac{1}{C}(\alpha w - q) &= P \\ L\ddot{q} + R\dot{q} - \frac{1}{C}(\alpha w - q) &= U \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

Due to the typically small values of L and C , simplifications are applied. Specifically, the inductance L , appearing in the numerator, is neglected, while the capacitance C , appearing in the denominator as $1/C$, contributes significantly and is retained. Furthermore, Equation (1a) is normalized by dividing through by the mass m . The simplified equations are then expressed as:

$$\begin{aligned} \ddot{w} + \omega_o^2 w + 2n\dot{w} + \alpha_1 \frac{1}{C}(\alpha w - q) &= P^* \\ R\dot{q} - \frac{1}{C}(\alpha w - q) &= U \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where:

$\omega_o^2 = \frac{k}{m}$ - ~~the~~ natural frequency,

$2n = \frac{c}{m}$ - ~~the~~ damping ratio,

$P^* = \frac{P}{m}$ - ~~the~~ mechanical force factor,

$\alpha_1 = \frac{\alpha}{m}$ - ~~an~~ additional parameter related to the coupling.

Figure 1. Schematic of the lumped electromechanical system model.

As mentioned earlier, either an amplifier or an energy harvester can be connected to the piezoelectric element. When only the amplifier is connected, the piezoelectric element operates as an actuator (i.e., $R=0, \Omega$). If the applied voltage U is constant, it induces a steady displacement w . In this case, the simplified form of Equations (2) becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \omega_o^2 w &= -\alpha_1 \frac{1}{C} (\alpha w - q) = \alpha_1 U \\ U &= -\frac{1}{C} (\alpha w - q) \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The electromechanical coupling coefficient α_1 can be determined from the relationship:

$$\alpha_1 = \frac{\omega_o^2 w}{U}. \quad (4)$$

In summary, the parameter α_1 can be estimated from a straightforward experimental procedure (referred to as TEST 1). A constant voltage U is applied, and the resulting steady-state displacement w is measured. Additionally, the natural frequency ω_o of the mechanical subsystem must be known.

In contrast, when only the energy harvester is connected, the external voltage U is zero. In this case, Equation (2b) simplifies to:

$$R\dot{q} + \frac{1}{C} q = \frac{\alpha}{C} w. \quad (5)$$

This represents a first-order linear ordinary differential equation. Assuming a harmonic mechanical excitation of the form $w=w_o \sin \omega t$, the amplitude of the resulting electric charge q_o is given by:

$$q_o = \frac{\alpha w_o}{\sqrt{1 + R^2 C^2 \omega^2}}. \quad (6)$$

The amplitude of the current flowing in the circuit is then:

$$\dot{q}_o = q_o \omega = \frac{\alpha w_o}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\omega^2} + R^2 C^2}}. \quad (7)$$

Consequently, the voltage amplitude across the load resistor is:

$$U_R = R\dot{q}_o = \frac{\alpha w_o}{\sqrt{\frac{1}{\omega^2 R^2} + C^2}}. \quad (8)$$

From Equation (8), the coupling coefficient α can be extracted as:

$$\alpha = \frac{U_R \sqrt{\frac{1}{\omega^2 R^2} + C^2}}{w_o}. \quad (9)$$

Based on Equation (9), a second experimental procedure (TEST 2) can be designed. Under periodic excitation at frequency ω , the displacement amplitude w_o of the mechanical system and the voltage amplitude U_R across the load resistor should be measured. In addition, the values of the load resistance R and the capacitance C must be known. By performing TEST 1 (Equation (4)) and TEST 2 (Equation (9)), the coupling coefficients α_I and α can be experimentally determined. These coefficients are subsequently used in the experimental analysis and theoretical modeling presented in the following sections.

3. Study of a cantilever beam with an embedded MFC patch

~~At the beginning of this section, the research object is described. taken Ff for the tests, are~~ six-layer beams ($[\pm 45/90]_s$) made from a glass-epoxy laminate ~~were used~~. The material properties and geometric dimensions of the beams are detailed in [7]. Specifically, a composite plate was produced in an autoclave, from which two sets of beams were cut ~~(2 × 3 rotor blades)~~. In principle, all beams were intended to have identical properties, including geometry, with cantilever length, width, and thickness equal to 316 mm, 34 mm, and 1.8 mm, respectively. Modal analysis confirmed that the properties were consistent across samples, with the error in the first natural frequency not exceeding 5%. Beams with the closest natural frequencies were selected for comparative studies. Subsequently, M8528-P1 or M8528-P2 patches were bonded onto the beams, resulting in two sets: three beams with P1 patches and three beams with P2 patches. Two types of experiments (TEST 1 and TEST 2) were conducted on these beams exhibiting the closest mechanical properties. A schematic of the test setup is shown in Fig. 2. The right side of the schematic depicts the amplifier (used in TEST 1), the electrodynamic shaker, and the harvester (used in TEST 2). The left side illustrates the method of measuring the beam response.

During the first, static test, the deflection of the beam tip was measured under the application of a constant voltage U to the MFC patch (actuator mode). The deflection was recorded using a camera, and the applied voltage was monitored via a voltmeter at the amplifier output. In the second, dynamic test, the beam vibrations were excited using the electrodynamic shaker, which induced voltage in the MFC patch (harvester mode). The voltage across the harvester resistor U_R was recorded using a voltmeter, while the beam vibrations were measured with an accelerometer. Since the accelerometer measures absolute acceleration \ddot{w}_a , but the relative acceleration \ddot{w}_o is required for calculations, the following relation at the resonance frequency ($\omega = \omega_o$) applies [12]:

$$\ddot{w}_o = \ddot{w}_a - a_{shaker}, \quad (10)$$

where : \ddot{w}_o , \ddot{w}_a and a_{shaker} denote the relative beam acceleration, absolute beam acceleration, and shaker acceleration amplitudes, respectively. This relation enables the determination of the beam vibration amplitude required for further analysis.

Fig.2. Schematic of the experimental setup.

3.1. Application of MFC as an actuator

In TEST 1, the voltage applied to the piezoelectric elements P1 or P2 was incrementally varied using an amplifier. These elements operate over different voltage ranges: from -500V to $+1500\text{V}$ for type P1, and from -60V to $+360\text{V}$ for type P2 [6]. During the tests, the voltage was increased from minimum to maximum in steps of 100V for P1 and 30V for P2. At each voltage level, photographs of the beam tip position were taken. To facilitate accurate measurements, a ruler was positioned near the beam tip, serving as a reliable reference scale. A series of photographs was collected for both types of elements. The paper presents one representative photograph each for the systems with P1 and P2 patches, showing the equilibrium position at 0V . Horizontal lines indicating successive beam tip positions were added to these images, while vertical arrows denote the direction of the amplifier voltage change. These annotated photographs are shown in Figs. 3 and 4.

Fig.3. Photograph showing results for the beam with P1 patch.

Fig.4. Photograph showing results for the beam with P2 patch.

Analysis of Figs. 3 and 4 reveals that, for the same voltage polarity, the beams deform in opposite directions: under positive voltage, the beam with the P1 element deflects downward, whereas the beam with the P2 element moves upward. This difference is attributed to the distinct piezoelectric mechanisms associated with the d33 and d31 effects. Using Equation (4) and applying the least squares method to the measurement data, the values of the coupling coefficient α_I were determined for both elements. The natural frequency value $\omega_0=47.91$ rad, discussed in Section 3.2, was used in the calculations. Fig. 5 illustrates the experimental relationship $w=f(U)$ along with its linear approximation.

Fig.5. Experimental and analytical trends of displacement w as a function of applied voltage U for (a) MFC-P1 and (b) MFC-P2.

From Equation (4), the α_I coefficients were calculated as $-22.04 \text{ ms}^{-2}\text{V}^{-1}$ for MFC-P1 and $42.92\text{ms}^{-2}\text{V}^{-1}$ for MFC-P2. Comparing the two MFC types reveals that the α_I coefficient for P2 is more than twice as large as that for P1, indicating that P2 is more effective in producing beam deformation per unit voltage. However, P2 exhibits a significant disadvantage: a smaller range of achievable displacement. Considering the displacement range $|w_{max}-w_{min}|$ observed in Fig. 5, the P1 type showed more than twice the displacement range of P2 (approximately 17

mm versus 8 mm). This highlights a clear conflict between actuation effectiveness and the operational displacement range for the two types of MFC elements.

3.2. Application of MFC as a harvester

In TEST 2, the electrodynamic shaker and the harvester played key roles. The shaker generated a kinematic excitation with a constant $a_{shaker}=0.4g$, while the frequency f was swept from 7 Hz to 8.5 Hz. The harvester consisted of a combination of resistors used to vary the load resistance R of the electrical circuit. A series of measurements were conducted with different load resistances: from 75 k Ω to 2200 k Ω for MFC-P1, and from 15 k Ω to 200 k Ω for MFC-P2. The resonance characteristics of the absolute vibration amplitude at the beam tip \ddot{w}_a and the voltage across the resistor U_R were recorded. The resulting characteristics are shown in Figs. 6 and 7.

Fig.6. Resonance characteristics for MFC-P1: (a) absolute beam vibration amplitude; (b) resistor voltage amplitude.

Fig.7. Resonance characteristics for MFC-P2: (a) absolute beam vibration amplitude; (b) resistor voltage amplitude.

Several observations can be made based on the resonance characteristics. First, the beam's natural frequency ω_o can be estimated from the frequency corresponding to the maximum amplitude, which was assumed to be $\omega_o=47.91\text{rad/s}$. Second, the vibration characteristics of

both beams should be nearly identical. However, slight differences visible in Figs. 6a and 7a may be attributed to structural differences between the MFC-P1 and MFC-P2 patches, as well as minor variations in the amount of adhesive applied during patch bonding. These factors likely caused the observed small discrepancies in resonance behavior. Furthermore, the load resistance does not significantly affect the beam's mechanical response; the vibration amplitude curves nearly overlap. This suggests that the electrical load resistance has negligible influence on the mechanical subsystem dynamics [13]. Lastly, the voltage U_R across the resistor depends on the load resistance. For the same beam vibration amplitude, higher load resistances produce larger voltage outputs.

Next, the electromechanical coupling coefficient α was determined from Equation (9). Calculations were performed using maximum amplitude values at $\omega=47.91\text{rad/s}$. The necessary relative vibration amplitudes \dot{w}_o were obtained from Equation (10). The resulting acceleration amplitudes were: 143.88ms^{-2} (corresponding to displacement amplitude $w_o=0.0627\text{m}$) for MFC-P1 and 127.58ms^{-2} (displacement amplitude 0.0556m) for MFC-P2. These displacement amplitudes correspond to approximately 20% of the beam length: $0.0627/0.316=0.198$ for P1 and $0.0556/0.316=0.176$ for P2. Such values indicate that large-amplitude beam vibrations were analyzed in this case. The capacitance C of the piezoelectric elements, needed for calculations, was measured as 7.14nF for MFC-P1 and 185.64nF for MFC-P2. Using Equation (9), the dependence $\alpha=f(R)$ was derived and is presented in Fig. 8.

Fig.8. Experimental dependence of the coupling coefficient α on load resistance R .

The trends observed in Fig. 8 are noteworthy. For the P2 element, the coefficient α remains approximately constant at around $2 \times 10^{-4} \text{C/m}$. This trend was determined over a narrow resistance range due to the voltage approaching its operational limit (approximately -60V during periodic signal). In contrast, the trend for the P1 element differs: the maximum α value occurs at low load resistances (about $0.75 \times 10^{-4} \text{C/m}$ at $75\text{k}\Omega$) and decreases with increasing resistance (to approximately $0.114 \times 10^{-4} \text{C/m}$ at $2200 \text{k}\Omega$). This suggests that while the P2 element is potentially more effective, its usable range is limited. In the present study (Fig. 7b), the P2 system operates near a critical case with maximum energy recovery (periodic voltage amplitude close to -60V). For the P1 system (Fig. 6b), similar voltage levels correspond to about 10% of its lower voltage limit (-500V). Consequently, the system with MFC-P1 can recover energy from vibrations approximately ten times larger than the system with MFC-P2. Generally, if the electromechanical model is accurate, the coefficient α should be constant. The observed nonlinear behavior may result from large beam deformations, necessitating nonlinear beam theory and higher-order deformation terms [14]. Although vibration amplitudes of both beams are similar (Figs. 6a and 7a), the trends $\alpha=f(R)$ differ substantially.

These discrepancies may arise from the capacitance C not being constant but varying periodically with vibration amplitude, i.e., $C=C(w)$. Under this assumption, Equation (5) should be modified as follows:

$$RC(w)\dot{q} + q = \alpha w. \quad (11)$$

This represents a first-order nonlinear ordinary differential equation due to the parametric dependence on $C(w)$. This hypothesis will be investigated in future work. A key question is why the effect of $C(w)$ appears more significant for the P1 element. This difference likely stems from the electrode configuration and corresponding piezoelectric effects. Capacitance depends on the distance between electrodes [15], which is defined differently for MFC-P1 and MFC-P2: it corresponds to the segment length in P1 and the element thickness in P2 [16]. The elongation of the MFC patch directly affects the electrode spacing in the d33 effect (P1), while for the d31 effect (P2), elongation indirectly influences the patch thickness (and thus electrode distance). This difference provides a plausible explanation for the contrasting trends observed in Fig. 8.

3.3. Summary of comparative studies

This subsection provides a concise summary of the results obtained from TEST 1 and TEST 2. The key parameters identified during the experiments are presented in Table 1. Values that are more favorable from a practical (user) perspective are highlighted in bold. The MFC-P2 element shows superior performance in columns 4 and 5, indicating higher electromechanical efficiency. In contrast, the MFC-P1 element outperforms in columns 6 and 7, which refer to its broader range of applicability - specifically, its ability to generate larger structural displacements or to harvest energy from higher-amplitude vibrations. These differences stem from the distinct piezoelectric effects employed in each element type and from structural differences, most notably reflected in the capacitance values (column 3). In conclusion, the selection of a suitable MFC type should be based on the specific requirements of the target application, particularly whether efficiency or operational range is prioritized.

Table 1. Comparison of selected parameter values for MFC-P1 and MFC-P2 elements.

Symbol	Parameter	Capacitance C (nF)	Parameter $ \alpha_1 $ ($\text{ms}^{-2}\text{V}^{-1}$)	Parameter $ \alpha $ (C/m)	Actuator $ w_{\max}-w_{\min} $ (mm)	Harvester $ U_{R\max}/U_{\text{downlimit}} $ (-)
M8528-P1	Value (V1)	7.14	22.04	$\langle 0.25, 0.114 \rangle$ $\times 10^{-4}$	17	0.1202
M8528-P2	Value (V2)	185.64	42.92	$\approx 2 \times 10^{-4}$	8	0.8464
-	Ratio $ V1/V2 $ (-)	0.0385	0.5135	$\langle 0.125, 0.057 \rangle$	2.125	0.1412

4. Study of cantilever bistable shell with an embedded MFC patch

This section presents an investigation of a different structure incorporating an MFC element - a bistable shell. As discussed in the previous chapter, the type of MFC element should be selected according to the characteristics of the host structure. In this case, the shell undergoes large deformations (strains), primarily due to two factors. First, a change in the equilibrium state results in a significant variation in strain - a persistent and substantial strain exists between the two stable configurations. Second, additional strain occurs during dynamic excitation, especially when snap-through behavior is induced. Considering these factors, the P1-type MFC element was deemed more suitable for this application. Fig. 9 shows the sequence of key states of the shell - from manufacturing to final installation.

Fig.9. Transformation path of the shell from manufacturing to clamping.

Further details regarding the geometry, materials, and fabrication process can be found in [9]. This paper focuses on aspects related to the selection and integration of the MFC patch. In brief, an eight-layer carbon-fiber shell with the stacking sequence $[45/-45_2/45/-45/45_2/-45]$ was manufactured using an autoclave process. The shell features variable curvature, radius ranging from 0.07 m to 0.114 m. After trimming to its final dimensions, the shell exhibited a free shape. Next, the MFC patch (model M2814-P1) was bonded to the shell. A small patch size was intentionally selected so as not to suppress the bistability and snap-through effect. Because bonding a patch to a curved surface poses difficulties, the shell was temporarily flattened during the gluing process. After the adhesive cured and the shell was released, it adopted a new free shape. Although the new geometry was only slightly altered compared to the original, residual strains developed in the MFC patch due to bonding in the flattened state. These pre-existing strains were disregarded during testing. A strain gauge was installed on the opposite side of the shell near the center of the MFC patch. It was zeroed (0 ppm) in the shell's new free state. The shell was then clamped to form a cantilever with an effective length of 0.018 m. Under these boundary conditions, the structure exhibited two stable equilibrium configurations, hereafter referred to as the I-shape and C-shape (Fig.9). Free vibration tests were carried out around each configuration to illustrate the dynamic characteristics of both equilibria (see Fig. 10).

Fig.10. Free vibrations initiated from: (a) I-equilibrium, (b) C-equilibrium.

The strain gauge mentioned earlier was used to measure the shell's dynamic response - specifically, the strain ϵ at a single location. Fig. 10 includes horizontal dashed lines indicating the strain gauge readings corresponding to the two stable equilibria: for example, $\epsilon=1350$ ppm in the C-equilibrium state. It is important to refer to the manufacturer's data [6], which specifies:

- Linear-elastic tensile strain limit: 1000ppm,
- Maximum operational tensile strain: <4500ppm.

Achieving snap-through requires much higher deformation - typically at least 2500 ppm - which may lead the MFC patch to exhibit nonlinear behavior.

During free vibration tests, the shell was deflected from each equilibrium to initiate oscillations. These initial conditions are marked with asterisks in Fig. 10. For both equilibrium states, two test cases were presented: one without snap-through and another where snap-through occurred. These tests also reveal the nature of vibrations around each equilibrium. Vibrations around the C-equilibrium are symmetric and resemble the response of a linear oscillator with low viscous damping. In contrast, vibrations around the I-equilibrium are distinctly different, resembling the response of systems with impact dynamics (e.g., a ball bouncing on a surface). To better investigate the shell's dynamic characteristics, additional tests were carried out using an electrodynamic shaker (TEST 2), where the MFC patch served as an energy harvester. In these tests, kinematic excitations with different excitation amplitudes a_{shaker} were applied, and frequency f sweeps from 5 to 10 Hz were conducted in both forward and backward directions. The harvester load resistance was set to $R=400$ k Ω . Resonance characteristics for selected excitation levels are shown in Figs. 11 and 12. These characteristics were recorded using LMS software with a harmonic estimator [17]. The resonance curve for C-mode vibrations displays the expected shape for a nearly linear system. However, at $a_{shaker}=0.8g$, a sudden amplitude jump and local distortion of the curve occur near 6 Hz (Fig. 12), indicating a snap-through event. This phenomenon corresponds to a transition from C-mode to I-mode vibrations and vice versa. The harmonic estimator struggles to accurately determine amplitude during such nonlinear transitions. The resonance behavior for I-mode vibrations is significantly more complex. At low excitation ($a_{shaker}=0.2g$), a pronounced softening effect is observed. At higher excitation ($a_{shaker}=0.8g$), the amplitude jump shifts toward lower frequencies, and a double vertical jump is visible during both forward and backward frequency sweeps - indicative of rich nonlinear dynamics.

Fig.11. Resonance curves for $a_{shaker}=0.2g$: (a) strain gauge signal , (b) voltage across the harvesting resistor.

Fig.12. Resonance curves for $a_{shaker}=0.8g$: (a) strain gauge signal , (b) voltage across the harvesting resistor. Resonance curves of strain gauge a) and resistor voltage b) for $a_{shaker}=0.8g$.

Applying the electromechanical lumped model from Section 2 to the bistable shell would require a major revision of the mechanical subsystem to account for strong nonlinearities. Capturing the asymmetric bistable behavior requires, at a minimum, a Duffing-Holmes-type model [18]. However, to fully represent the local dynamic variations observed, a higher-order description is needed. As proposed in [19], a fifth-order polynomial may be used to approximate the nonlinear restoring forces more accurately. Due to the complexity of the dynamic behavior, this study focused on estimating the electromechanical coupling coefficient α using the relationship defined in Equation (9) - TEST 2, which does not take into account the mechanical subsystem's properties. The following parameters and assumptions were used:

- Excitation frequencies corresponding to natural frequencies: 6.5Hz (C-mode) and 9.1 Hz (I-mode),
- Capacitance of the M2814-P1 patch: $C=1.176nF$ (measured),
- Load resistance: $R=400 k\Omega$,
- Resistor voltage amplitude U_R and strain ϵ were taken from the resonance characteristics.

Instead of displacement amplitude w_o , strain ϵ was used in the calculations. The resulting values of α as a function of excitation level a_{shaker} are shown in Fig. 13.

a) b)

Fig.13. Electromechanical coupling coefficient α as a function of excitation amplitude a_{shaker} for (a) $f=5.5\text{Hz}$ and (b) $f=9.1\text{Hz}$.

Analyzing the trends $\alpha=f(a_{shaker})$, it can be observed that near the resonance in the I-mode, the coupling coefficient α is higher for the I-mode vibration (Fig. 13b). Beyond the absolute values, a noticeable difference is seen in the shapes of the curves corresponding to I- and C-mode vibrations. For C-mode vibrations, the trend exhibits relatively low variability and could, in a rough approximation, be considered constant. In contrast, such simplification would not be justified for the I-mode, where the coupling coefficient varies more significantly with excitation. However, near the resonance in the C-mode, the α coefficient is initially higher for the C-mode vibration (Fig. 13a). At an excitation level of $a_{shaker}=0.6\text{g}$, two stable solutions coexist. A transition (jump) to a higher amplitude response in the I-mode alters the relationship between the α values for the I- and C-modes. The trends obtained at a constant load resistance suggest that the coupling coefficient α is affected by nonlinearities. In this system, the MFC patch undergoes significant deformation, which may influence its capacitance and contribute to the nonlinear behavior discussed in the previous section. It should also be noted that in this study, strain measurements were taken at a single point, whereas energy harvesting occurs over the entire active surface of the MFC. If the strain distribution across the MFC area changes significantly with vibration amplitude, local strain gauge readings might not accurately represent the overall deformation, potentially affecting the observed trend shapes in Fig. 13. Furthermore, according to some researchers, time and temperature effects alone can influence the α coefficient in the d33 mode [20], which should be taken into account in future studies.

5. Conclusions

The primary objective of this study was to answer two questions:

1. Which MFC element - P1 or P2 - is more effective? and
2. Which of these elements is more suitable for energy harvesting from the mechanical vibrations of bistable shells?

Both questions were addressed to a significant extent. Section 3 presented a detailed comparative analysis of the P1 and P2 elements, and the results were summarized in Subsection 3.3. The answer to the first question is not straightforward: the P2 element demonstrates higher electromechanical effectiveness, while the P1 element offers a broader operational range. Therefore, selecting the appropriate MFC type must be based on the specific requirements and characteristics of the target application.

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This principle was applied to the bistable shell system. After careful analysis, a compact P1-type patch was chosen. The key challenge in this case was the high level of deformation (strain), which approaches the operational limits of the MFC material. Despite prolonged operation under these conditions, the P1 element remained functional and undamaged.

The experimental results confirmed that the P1 patch can successfully harvest energy from mechanical vibrations around both stable equilibria of the bistable shell. During the study, it became clear that the capacitance of the MFC patch should be more closely examined, and the adopted electromechanical model may require modification—particularly for the P1 element.

This refinement is planned for future work.

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